

**A CORRELATION STUDY OF SPIRITUAL INTELLIGENCE AND
EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE OF SENIOR SECONDARY
SCHOOL TEACHER**

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ABSTRACT

Teachers are the architects of the future. It is therefore, essential that teachers should possess spiritual intelligence and emotional intelligence. The present study aims to investigate the relationship between spiritual intelligence and emotional intelligence of senior secondary school teachers of district Saharanpur. The teachers working in senior secondary schools situated in district Saharanpur are constituted the population for the present study. 100 teachers were selected by adopting random sampling technique. Mean and coefficient of correlation were used for the statistical analysis. Findings revealed that spiritual intelligence does not affect emotional intelligence of senior secondary school male and female teachers.

KEYWORDS: Spiritual Intelligence, Emotional Intelligence.

INTRODUCTION

Education plays a very important role in the development of a child's personality. Education is pre-requisite for national, regional and global development. This development can take place when we have quality teachers who are emotionally competent, involved in their jobs, committed to teaching, having positive attitude towards teaching profession and equipped with necessary knowledge, skills and competencies for effective teaching. The work, in which teacher is engaged, would be meaningful and useful to the society. And the teaching will be fruitful only when

it is done with responsibilities, not just in terms of its execution. When teacher is involved in his job, he can be productive to himself and students. The degree to which an employee is engaged in and enthusiastic about performing his work is considered as job involvement.

It is true that schools are the nurseries of the nation and teachers are the architect of the future. Thus, in the deteriorating situations where the teacher face tough competitions and rapid changes in life and feel stress, anxiety, frustration and many more psychological disorders, it is quite essential in the contemporary education system to maintain an emotional balance in one slife. It is now supposed that teachers, especially senior secondary school teachers should acquire a balanced spiritual and emotional intelligence to diminish the anxieties, frustrations. It will eliminate their problem.

AIM OF THE STUDY

“The main purpose of the study was to find out the Relationship Between Spiritual Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence of Senior Secondary School Teachers.”

Objectives of the study

1. To study the relationship between spiritual intelligence and emotional intelligence of senior secondary school Teach
2. To study the relationship between spiritual and emotional intelligence of male teacher of senior secondary school.
3. To study the relationship between spiritual and emotional intelligence of female senior secondary school teacher.

HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

Following will be Null Hypothesis:-

1. These exists no significant relationship between spiritual intelligence and emotional intelligence of senior secondary school Teacher.
2. There is no significant relationship between spiritual intelligence and emotional intelligence of senior secondary school male teachers.

No significant relationship exists between spiritual intelligence and emotional intelligence of senior secondary school female teachers.

DELIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The purposed study was delimited to teachers of senior secondary school of district Saharanpur. The study involved both the male and female teachers.

METHODOLOGY

The present study was attempted to seek the facts with regard to the existing relationship between spiritual intelligence and emotional intelligence of senior secondary school teachers. So the normative survey research method was adopted in the present research work.

POPULATION OF THE STUDY

The teachers working in the senior secondary schools situated in district Saharanpur constituted the population for the present study.

SAMPLE OF THE STUDY

100 Teachers working in senior secondary schools of Saharanpur district were randomly selected. Among them 50 were male and 50 were female teachers.

TOOLS USED

For the present study, following tools were used :

1. Roquan Spiritual intelligence test for measuring spiritual intelligence by Prof. RoquiyaZainuddin, chairman, Dept. of Education. AMU and Ms. Anjum Ahmed, Researcher scholar Dept. of Education, AMU (Aligarh).
2. Roquan Emotional intelligence Test developed by Prof. RoquiyaZainuddin and Anjum Ahmed.

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUE

Mean and coefficient of correlation test were used for the statistical analysis.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Table 1

Showing the relationship between spiritual and emotional intelligence of senior secondary school teachers

Category	No. of teachers	Mean	r	Level of significance
Spiritual intelligence	100	305.00	.513	Significant at .01 level
Emotional intelligence	100	69.11		

Total value at – .05 - .195 .01 - .254

The above table shows that the calculated value of correlation coefficient is positive. It can be interpreted that spiritual intelligence and emotional intelligence of senior secondary school teacher are positively and moderately correlated with each other. This value is also significant at 0.01 level of significance. Hence, rejecting the null hypothesis and it may be concluded that there is a significant relationship between spiritual intelligence and emotional intelligence of senior secondary school teachers.

Table 2

Showing the correlation between spiritual intelligence and emotional intelligence of male senior secondary school teachers.

Category	No. of male teachers	M	r	Level of significance
Spiritual intelligence	50	308.66	.0239	Insignificant
Emotional intelligence	50	69.08		

Table value - .05 - .283 .01 - .354

The above table shows that correlation coefficient between spiritual intelligence and emotional intelligence of male senior secondary school teacher comes out to be +0.239, this is insignificant at both levels of significance.

It can be interpreted that spiritual intelligence and emotional intelligence of male senior secondary school teachers are insignificantly related with each other. Hence,

accepting the null hypothesis, it is concluded that there is low, positive and insignificant relationship between spiritual intelligence and emotional intelligence of male senior secondary school teachers.

Table 3

Showing the correlation between spiritual intelligence and emotional intelligence of female senior secondary school teachers.

CATEGORY	No.	Mean	R	Level of Significance
Spiritual Intelligence	50	305.00	+.114	Insignificant at both level
Emotional Intelligence	50	69.14		

value at level - .05 - .273

.01 - .354

This table shows that correlation coefficient between spiritual intelligence and emotional intelligence of female senior secondary school teachers is positive and very low. Also this value is insignificant at both levels. Hence, accepting the null hypothesis, it may be concluded that there is not a significant relationship between spiritual intelligence and emotional intelligence of female of senior secondary school.

CONCLUSIONS

On the basis of analysis and interpretation of data, Senior secondary teachers have a positive, moderate and significant correlation between spiritual intelligence and emotional intelligence. But spiritual and emotional intelligence of male and female teachers of senior secondary schools are positively correlated but this relationship is insignificant. It shows that as spiritual intelligence increases, emotional intelligence also increases.

IMPLICATIONS OF THE STUDY

The present study is useful for present scenario as well as for future. It is useful for parents ,teachers and also for students. With the help of this study we can understand how spiritual intelligence is related to emotional intelligence and how can we improve the spiritual intelligence with the help of emotional intelligence. The problem of indiscipline in society, homes can easily solve by this study. in reference of teachers present study is meaningful and useful. Present study helps to understand the emotional intelligence and spiritual intelligence and use it to grow up on various ways of success.

The most important aspect of study is that it is more useful for a teacher. With the help of this study teachers is able to self assessment, know his emotion) .so that he can use them in an appropriate way, leveraging his own and other's emotions to carry out his responsibilities and reach his aspirations.

Once teacher is aware of how emotions affects his attitude, behavior and society towards situations he will be able to self manage by understanding and being able to control his emotions .It is hoped that these findings will become worthwhile material for existing domain of education.

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